

Preparing Citizens for Emergency Calls with a Hybrid FSM-LLM Dialogue Agent

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Emergency calls are time-critical, verbal-only interactions in which call takers must assess severity and make decisions based solely on the caller’s description. Effective communication is critical during these calls, especially since most callers are inexperienced and untrained due to the rarity of emergency situations. To address this challenge, we develop a task-oriented dialogue agent that simulates emergency call takers to prepare citizens for effective medical emergency communication. It combines a finite-state machine-based dialogue policy for structured, protocol-guided interactions with large language model-based understanding to map caller descriptions to structured symptoms. Our dialogue policy improves both classification accuracy and dialogue efficiency while maintaining naturalness, as shown in a user study with human participants.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: task-oriented dialogue, emergency calls, citizen preparedness, large language models, applied artificial intelligence

1 Introduction

In emergency calls, citizens have to communicate critical information verbally without visual cues. Moreover, these situations are highly time-critical, as delays in cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) and defibrillation significantly reduce survival in cardiac arrest cases [14]. However, inadequate preparedness among citizens remains a critical factor in delayed emergency response and poor patient outcomes [20]. Therefore, we propose the use of task-oriented dialogue (TOD) systems simulating emergency call dispatchers to give citizens the opportunity to prepare for more effective emergency communication.

Unlike conversational chatbots that engage in open-ended dialogues, TOD systems are designed to assist users in achieving specific goals through structured information gathering in conversation. They contain multiple common components [13]:

- (1) natural language understanding (NLU) for mapping user utterances to a structured representation (slots);
- (2) dialogue state tracking (DST) for maintaining a register of these set slots;
- (3) a dialogue policy that uses information from the DST to determine the next dialogue action; and
- (4) natural language generation (NLG) to create coherent and natural system utterances.

However, defining these components for medical emergency calls is not straightforward. Emergency calls require simultaneous interpretation of flawed lay descriptions while prioritizing the questions that matter most. Real-world evidence shows that decision-making can delay the recognition of time-critical needs in emergency dispatch [26]. At the same time, large language models (LLMs) alone underperform on explicit DST in TOD [9]. These constraints motivate our focus on an interpretable dialogue state representation and a tightly controlled dialogue policy. In this work, we present a dialogue agent that simulates emergency call takers to help prepare citizens for medical emergency calls. Our contributions are:

- We propose a DST model that decomposes broad dialogue outcome categories into fine-grained and interpretable slots with semantic meaning to improve transparency compared to conventional black-box methods.

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- We implement a dialogue policy through an extended finite-state machine (FSM) to make dialogue flow controllable and traceable without relying on the dialogue history directly.
- In a user study, we demonstrate that our system outperforms an LLM-only baseline both in emergency classification and dialogue efficiency while preserving perceived naturalness.

2 Related Work

Recent work on task-oriented dialogue often explores whether a single instruction-following LLM can replace traditional modular TOD systems. Prominent examples of this direction formulate task completion as autonomous action selection by a general-purpose LLM rather than by explicit modules [33]. At the same time, previously gathered evidence suggests that end-to-end systems remain weak precisely at the step most critical, which is DST. In particular, LLM-based systems can produce plausible responses, yet still underperform when user utterances must be converted into appropriate and actionable dialogue state updates [9]. Related findings are reported for conversational slot filling, where topic shifts, interruptions, and implicit references make direct zero-shot extraction difficult in realistic dialogue streams. This motivates architectures that combine LLM understanding with more controlled downstream components [23]. Taken together, this suggests that robust task completion still benefits from separating semantic interpretation from dialogue control.

TOD systems excel as automated assistance systems in safety- or time-critical domains, e.g. as in-vehicle assistants, whether for car drivers [11], or aircraft pilots [10], as well as in various healthcare applications [28]. While LLMs have started to see adoption as stand-alone solutions for these tasks, they are still insufficient to fully replace traditional TOD systems in critical applications [9]. In worst-case scenarios, the LLMs hallucinate information and generate behaviour with dangerous safety implications [30]. Further, LLMs struggle to maintain the policy during these scenarios; they lose focus and lack the ability to steer the conversation [1]. In this work, we focus on the classification of medical emergencies. This task can be viewed as a form of patient diagnosis. However, the research in that field focuses on disease diagnosis and clinical medicine [27]. Unlike emergency calls, those conversations are typically not time-critical and focus on different symptom groups. Likewise, these approaches perform one-shot classification while ignoring incremental symptom acquisition as a necessary pre-step [34]. Moreover, the dialogues studied are often conversational and require a sufficiently trained domain expert to guide the system toward the goal [15, 18].

When time-critical emergency settings are considered, previous research has approached them mainly as a training problem. Existing work focuses on first aid [2], the correct use of fire extinguishers and fire safety training in general [16, 22]. For communication training in emergency situations, prior research has shown that regular training of emergency call dispatchers is beneficial for the accurate detection of cardiac arrest cases [8, 19]. We argue that raising citizens' awareness is equally important and that improving their preparedness is more beneficial than real-world automation. This enables necessary information to be provided quickly and accurately, maximizing the chance of patient survival [29]. While research exists on training of emergency call dispatchers using LLM-based approaches to simulate emergency callers [4], no previous research focused on preparing citizens for emergency calls has been conducted to the best of our knowledge. In contrast, attempts to integrate LLMs into real-world emergency dispatch systems are more frequent [7, 21]. As these systems are designed to support dispatchers in real-time rather than to replace them, they cannot be repurposed for educational uses targeting citizens.

3 Problem Statement for Emergency Determination

Let U_u and U_a be the space of utterances emitted by the user u (i.e. caller) and an agent a (i.e. a simulated call-taker of an emergency dispatch centre) respectively. We model an emergency call as a sequence of alternating utterances over T dialogue turns:

$$\mathcal{D}_{1:T} := (u_{a,1}, u_{u,1}, u_{a,2}, u_{u,2}, \dots, u_{a,T}, u_{u,T}), \quad (1)$$

where $u_{a,t} \in U_a$ and $u_{u,t} \in U_u$, and $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$. The dialogue state B_t at dialogue turn t is defined by the tuple $B_t := (M_t, S_t, O_t)$. $M_t \in \mathcal{M}$ denotes a partial map $K_M \rightarrow V_M$ for dialogue turn t , with K_M being the set of metadata identifiers (e.g. caller's name, emergency location) and the respective values from V_M . Note that M_t is only defined for $k_M \in K_M$ for which corresponding information $v_M \in V_M$ has already been extracted, i.e. $\text{dom}(M_t) \subseteq K_M$. Likewise, $S_t \in \mathcal{S}$ denotes a partial map $K_S \rightarrow V_S$ with K_S being identifiers for symptoms (e.g. breathing, responsiveness, intoxication level), while $O_t \in \mathcal{O}$ denotes a partial map $K_O \rightarrow V_O$ with K_O being identifiers for inferred higher-level emergency call outcomes and the respective values from V_O . These outcomes are protocol-defined classifications that determine the required response. K_M, K_S, K_O are disjoint sets. Slot filling is the process of progressively updating B_t with each dialogue turn t , with $B_0 := (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset)$.

Given the user utterance $u_{u,t} \in U_u$ at dialogue turn t , NLU extracts a partial map $\Delta_t := f_{\text{NLU}}(u_{u,t})$, which defines respective updates to V_M and V_S , with f_{NLU} being:

$$f_{\text{NLU}} : U_u \rightarrow \mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{S}. \quad (2)$$

Metadata and symptoms are updated by overwriting $v_M \in V_M$ and $v_S \in V_S$, if Δ_t is defined for the corresponding k :

$$M_{t+1}(k) = \begin{cases} \Delta_t(k), & k \in K_M, \\ M_t(k), & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$S_{t+1}(k) = \begin{cases} \Delta_t(k), & k \in K_S, \\ S_t(k), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Emergency call outcomes are inferred from the updated symptom state

$$f_O : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{O}, \quad (5)$$

and we obtain the next dialogue state:

$$B_{t+1} := (M_{t+1}, S_{t+1}, O_{t+1}). \quad (6)$$

After computing B_{t+1} , the dialogue policy chooses the next dialogue action $a_{t+1} \in A$:

$$f_{\text{pol}} : \mathcal{B} \rightarrow A, \quad a_{t+1} := f_{\text{pol}}(B_{t+1}). \quad (7)$$

If necessary the NLG component generates the next agent utterance $u_{a,t+1} \in U_a$:

$$f_{\text{NLG}} : A \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow U_a, \quad u_{a,t+1} := f_{\text{NLG}}(a_{t+1}, B_{t+1}). \quad (8)$$

The termination decision is defined as follows. Let $X_{t+1} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicate whether the call can be ended after updating to B_{t+1} :

$$f_{\text{term}} : \mathcal{B} \rightarrow X, \quad X = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if call can be ended,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Then, the goal of an emergency call for some $t \geq 0$ is,

$$(\text{dom}(O_{t+1}) \neq \emptyset) \wedge (X_{t+1} = 1), \quad (10)$$

where $\text{dom}(O_{t+1})$ are the $k \in K_O$ for which O_{t+1} returns a value $v \in V_O$. Achieving this goal can be optimized via two objectives. Let $S_f \in \mathcal{S}$ denote the final symptom state at the final dialogue turn T and let $S^* : K_S \rightarrow V_S$ denote the non-partial map of the target symptom state. Then, the first objective is to maximize the number of correctly identified symptoms,

$$\max |\{k \in \text{dom}(S_f) \mid S_f(k) = S^*(k)\}|,$$

and the second objective is to minimize the total number of dialogue turns,

$$\min T.$$

4 FSM for Task-Oriented Dialogue

We model dialogue phases using an extended finite-state machine (EFSM). This facilitates meaningful abstractions over a regular FSM. We adopt the definition from Kalaji et al. [12]; an EFSM is a tuple (N, n_0, n_t, V, I, T) :

- N is the set of nodes. Each node represents a semantic step in the processing of the TOD. At each node the system can linger for a variable amount of time.
- $n_0 \in N$ is the initial node.
- $n_t \in N$ is the terminal node which signifies that the emergency call can be ended.
- V is the set of global variables. We define a tuple $V := (B_t, Q)$ where B_t is the dialogue state and Q is an ordered set of questions as formulated in official protocols developed by domain experts.
- I is the set of input declarations. An input $i \in I$ can either be an utterance u , an output of $f_{\text{NLU}}, f_{\text{pol}}, f_{\text{NLG}}, f_{\text{term}}$ or an updated dialogue state B_{t+1} .
- T is the set of transitions. A transition $t \in T$ is defined by a tuple (n, n', i, g, op) where $n, n' \in N$ are the start and target node of the transition. $i \in I$ are the input parameters, g is a guard, which needs to be satisfied for t to occur, and op is an operation that executes as part of t .

Guards g are used to define conditions over the questions Q , the termination decision X and the dialogue outcome map O_{t+1} . Operations op define side effects during execution of the EFSM, such as forwarding an agent utterance u_a to the user, or invoke the functions as described in the problem statement. This extension of a regular FSM by guards g , operations op and global variables $v \in V$ allows the dialogue flow to be defined independently of the actual set of questions and variables necessary to complete an emergency call. Instead, nodes represent reusable dialogue actions, with node execution parametrized by the global state variables v . For example, instead of defining a separate node for each pre-defined question, a single node repeatedly retrieves and removes the next question from Q when activated. Likewise, it is not necessary to define each $S_t \in \mathcal{S}$ as a separate node in the EFSM; a single node operates on all possible B_{t+1} instead.

Inputs, guards, and operations are optional for each transition t . For example, the outgoing transition from n_0 has neither input nor guard, as this is the only transition that can be taken at the beginning of a dialogue. Likewise, every user utterance $u_u \in U_u$ is parsed unconditionally in n_{parse} and thus, there is no guard defined. The transition from n_{parse} is also not defined by guards, but by the value returned by f_{NLU} , which is the op of the incoming transition, and subsequently used as inputs for the outgoing transitions.

Fig. 1. Extended finite-state machine used as dialogue policy. Nodes denote processing stages, and edges show inputs, guards, and operations. A double border indicates the terminal node.

Figure 1 illustrates how the FSM is used to control the dialogue flow. During the main cycle of an emergency call, n_{PickQ} picks questions $q \in Q$ and forwards them to the user (i.e. n_{Ask}). For each user response u_u , $f_{NLU}(u_u)$ is performed by the LLM during n_{Parse} . If no new dialogue state can be extracted, i.e. $B_{t+1} = B_t$, f_{NLU} returns a new question directly and we immediately return to n_{Ask} . Otherwise, f_{NLU} returns an update to the dialogue state. The merged state B_{t+1} then is evaluated in n_{Eval} . If an dialogue outcome has not been reached, i.e. $dom(O_{t+1}) = \emptyset$, a new q is selected. However, if $dom(O_{t+1}) \neq \emptyset$, f_{term} computes X_{t+1} during the transition to n_{Out} . If $X_{t+1} = 0$, f_{NLG} generates a custom question. Else, a final dialogue outcome has been determined and the call can be ended. This creates a cycle that repeats until the dialogue policy reaches a definite, higher-level outcome, or no further questions are available.

4.1 Implementing a Dialogue State Model for Medical Emergency Calls

We consider a symptom state model S comprising a total of 71 symptoms K_S , which can be considered binary variables indicating the presence or absence of specific symptoms. These symptoms are derived from official emergency call protocols [24] and are categorized into two groups: 22 symptoms $k_{RD1} \in K_S$ related to the dialogue outcome group called RD1 and 49 symptoms $k_{RD2} \in K_S$ related to the dialogue outcome group called RD2. The former are broader and signify the necessity of an ambulance, while the latter are more specific, always correspond to one RD1 label, and indicate that an emergency physician is needed. Furthermore, some RD2 symptoms are CPR-indicative, i.e. $k_{CPR} \in K_S$. Hence, the case is treated as cardiac arrest. The names of these groups are motivated by the emergency medical services (EMS) materials used for reference [3, 24]. These three emergency call outcomes make up K_O and build a hierarchy, where $CPR \Rightarrow RD2 \Rightarrow RD1$. We define the final dialogue outcome as the set label highest in that hierarchy. Each is set independent of the other two, if at least one corresponding symptom in K_S is set. The metadata state model M consists of variables that capture essential information about the caller and the emergency situation, such as the caller's name and the location. They are not considered for the final outcome classification. All variables in the dialogue

Fig. 2. System architecture of the two dialogue agents. Shared components are shown in yellow; the FSM+LLM agent is shown at the top in blue, and the LLM-only baseline is shown at the bottom in red.

state are initialized as unknown at the beginning of an emergency call. In a typical emergency call, we expect only a few symptoms to be actually set, while the majority remain unknown throughout the interaction.

4.2 System Architecture and Implementation of a Dialogue Agent

Figure 2 illustrates our proposed system compared to a baseline. NLU and DST function similar in both approaches; a LLM with comparable setup is used to extract the state update function Δ_t . As it overwrites old values with new ones, Δ_t enables the system to accumulate dialogue state over multiple turns, but also to incorporate corrections if necessary. We withhold the conversation history only from the FSM-based architecture to reduce the size of the unstructured context handed to the LLM. The same is not possible for the baseline as it relies on the history to avoid repeating questions. Whenever the next dialogue action involves dialogue state elicitation, the FSM tries to pick pre-defined questions from Q and falls back to the LLM-based NLG when necessary. This potentially reduces the response time of the system. In our implementation, a LLM is still responsible for making the termination decision f_{term} . When a RD1 outcome has been reached, there may still be a possibility to change the final dialogue outcome. In such cases the LLM decides, based on B_t , whether to continue asking for further information or to end the call.

The dialogue state B is implemented using the Python library Pydantic¹. We use the graph module of PydanticAI² to define and execute the EFSM and to handle calls to LLMs.³ For all invocations of LLM in either agent, we used Google’s Gemini 2.5 Flash with temperature set to zero and all remaining parameters left at their defaults. This decision was motivated by latency considerations to reduce waiting times, user frustration, and participant dropout during the validation study. Three system prompts were designed, two for the FSM-based agent and one for the baseline. To

¹Pydantic Website: <https://docs.pydantic.dev/>

²PydanticAI Website: <https://ai.pydantic.dev>

³Upon acceptance and publication of the paper, all source code and data will be made publicly available.

improve comparability between both agents, system prompts only differ where required by the underlying architecture. Table 1 summarizes the resulting prompt design: merged cells indicate prompt sections shared across all variants, whereas the separated columns highlight task- or policy-specific instructions. To facilitate slot-filling, the LLM has access to a schema of our dialogue state model to ensure consistent state structure. Most system utterances are not generated by an LLM but selected by the FSM. Hence, the FSM-based agent received no instructions regarding the generation of questions about the dialogue state. LLMs are only used to generate custom questions when no suitable predefined utterance is available. In contrast, the baseline relies on a single prompt to handle all TOD processes jointly.

4.3 Example Dialogue Trace

A real interaction with the system is shown in Table 2 with EFSM-node execution, dialogue state updates, and policy decisions. The dialogue is taken from the user study. As per protocol, the dialogue starts collecting general information. In this case, the NLU detects a medical emergency, but no specific symptoms can be extracted from the callers' situation description yet. In an ideal scenario, the caller provides sufficient information to form a dispatch decision immediately. However, in reality, this is rarely the case. Therefore, the system starts asking questions related to medical emergencies from Q . Their order is already optimized for likelihood and severity of symptoms in order to increase efficiency. In this example the second symptom-related question triggers a preliminary dialogue outcome. An intentionally open question elicits more information to decide if the outcome level needs to be raised, which is not the case here. Hence, the system decides to dispatch an ambulance without asking further questions. This happens via the follow-up decision prompt as described in Table 1. This example shows how the proposed architecture achieves protocol-compliant and traceable dialogue management. It also illustrates how the system handles a realistic, usually non-linear dialogue flow. For example, the system never asked about signs of paralysis directly, but was still able to extract this information from the caller's response. This is a common event in real emergency calls, where callers provide relevant information without being explicitly asked for it. A naive implementation with strictly linear logic would have failed to extract such information.

5 User Study and Evaluation

To validate our implementation, we conduct a user study with human participants. As a baseline, we use a dialogue agent which relies entirely on a LLM with a single prompt as shown in Figure 2. The system prompt carries relevant information about the rules of the dialogue, which are encoded in the FSM of our solution. In contrast, the baseline has access to the entire conversation history, but not to Q .

Ten study participants took part in the validation. Each was tasked to simulate the caller for a set of pre-defined scenarios describing medical emergencies with varying degrees of information. Scenario descriptions are based on scenarios used for dispatcher training [3] and were accessible both before and during each simulated call of the study. Furthermore, participants followed the assigned scenario closely, while improvising whenever necessitated by the scenario. After each call, participants answered a short questionnaire. Policy assignment was performed by simple randomization at the call level. Agent randomization was done without informing the participants, who interacted with the dialogue agents through a web interface; user input, system output and scenario descriptions were entirely text-based.

Ground truth (GT) annotations are manually created and double-checked based on the scenarios designed by domain experts. Each GT specifies the minimal necessary state required to reach an intended dialogue outcome while assuming that the reference dialogue protocol is followed. Because dialogue-specific variations caused by humans and LLMs

Table 1. Comparison of the three prompt variants. Instructions shared across all variants are shown in merged rows; prompt-specific instructions are shown in separate columns.

	State extraction prompt for f_{NLU}	Follow-up decision prompt for f_{term}	Baseline prompt (LLM-Only)
Role	You are a professional emergency call taker in an emergency call centre. Your job is to calmly ask focused questions and capture structured, factual information about the situation in the provided data model. You do not give medical advice; you only gather information.		
Task	Gather the minimum necessary information efficiently. Extract and validate facts from the user’s statements. Only ask questions that help populate or verify fields in the data model.		
	You receive a user-provided answer to a question about the situation. Extract values from the answer that fit the variables defined in the model.	Decide if enough information has been gathered based on the current state to make a final decision. If not, provide a contextual and concise follow-up question. Try to ensure that you understand the situation well enough to make a decision.	You receive a phone call from a caller who wants to report an emergency. First, present an appropriate greeting. Then, begin determining the basic information about the emergency. The outcome and dispatch decisions are determined automatically by other systems. This is time-critical, so keep the conversation efficient and to the point.
Rules	If something is unclear or ambiguous, ask a short follow-up question to clarify. Ask only one question at a time. Prefer simple, layperson language and short explanations; avoid jargon. Do not repeat questions whose answers are already clearly known, unless you need to verify, resolve ambiguity, or resolve a contradiction. Maintain a single language throughout the interaction; use the language of the user’s first message and do not switch languages mid-interaction. Confirmations like ‘okay’ or ‘yes’ are acknowledgements and do not change factual fields unless they clearly answer a question.		
	Never invent or guess values. Only set fields when the user explicitly provided the information or it follows unambiguously. If you cannot extract any new values, ask a single open follow-up question ONLY if it is likely to enable extracting new state. When you cannot extract new data, you are not allowed to ask for specific fields directly; ask a single open follow-up question. Use None for unknown values. Never ask the exact same question twice in a row.	Do not return a new question when enough information has been gathered and further questions are not needed. Evaluate completeness of metadata fields like caller name and location. Consult the conversation history to avoid repeating questions. The contextual question should only ask for fields from state if they are potentially related to already set state.	Only ask questions needed for personalia or RD1-related variables. Do not ask directly about RD2 symptoms. Never say “RD1”, “RD2”, “schema”, “JSON”, or “State” to the caller. Only once at least one outcome is true should the prompt decide whether more questions are needed.
Decisions	If the caller’s reply does not clearly support setting a field, set it to False. Do not repeat questions. Stop asking new questions once the required information has been gathered as far as reasonably possible. This is a time-critical dialogue. Minimize the number of questions asked while ensuring safety and completeness. Use the provided schema to understand which fields belong to personalia and which correspond to RD1 and RD2. Continue asking targeted questions only as needed to determine and fill RD1-related variables. Only AFTER RD1 is true are you allowed to ask for more details in a single generic and open question. Do not mention RD2 or any RD2 symptom names directly in this question. Do not ask any additional new questions specifically targeting RD2 symptoms after this generic question.		
	Verify whether the caller answered the last question; if not, you may re-ask it once.	When the current state is sufficient for decision-making, do not provide a next question. This is a time-critical dialogue. Minimize the number of questions asked while ensuring safety and completeness.	Use the provided schema to understand which fields belong to personalia and which correspond to RD1 and RD2. Continue asking targeted questions only as needed to determine and fill RD1-related variables. Only AFTER RD1 is true are you allowed to ask for more details in a single generic and open question. Do not mention RD2 or any RD2 symptom names directly in this question. Do not ask any additional new questions specifically targeting RD2 symptoms after this generic question.

Table 2. Example Dialogue from user study. Caller turns are shaded in gray for readability. Each row shows the internal FSM processing with the resulting DST update and policy output.

Speaker	Utterance	FSM Step	DST Update	Decision
Dispatcher	Hello! You're speaking with the emergency call services.	$n_0 \rightarrow n_{Eval} \rightarrow n_{PickQ}$		Caller name
Dispatcher	With whom am I speaking, please?	n_{Ask}		
Caller	Hello this is John Doe.	$n_{Parse} \rightarrow n_{Eval} \rightarrow n_{PickQ}$	caller_name = John Doe	Location
Dispatcher	Where exactly is the emergency location?	n_{Ask}		
Caller	I'm at 123 Main Street!	$n_{Parse} \rightarrow n_{Eval} \rightarrow n_{PickQ}$	location = 123 Main Street	Overall Situation
Dispatcher	What has just happened acutely?	n_{Ask}		
Caller	Nothing happened to me, but my wife is acting weird.	$n_{Parse} \rightarrow n_{Eval} \rightarrow n_{PickQ}$	emergency_type = medical <i>Could not set specific symptoms</i>	Breathing [RD1]
Dispatcher	Is the patient getting enough air now?	n_{Ask}		
Caller	Yes, she can breathe fine.	$n_{Parse} \rightarrow n_{Eval} \rightarrow n_{PickQ}$	now_insufficient_air = false	Responsiveness [RD1]
Dispatcher	Is the patient reacting normally now when spoken to?	n_{Ask}		
Caller	No, she is slurring her words and sounds weird.	$n_{Parse} \rightarrow n_{Eval} \rightarrow n_{Out}$	acute_speech_disorder = true rd1 = true	Check for RD2
Dispatcher	Can you describe the situation with more detail?	n_{Ask}		
Caller	About three quarters of an hour ago my wife started speaking weirdly, and now she can't use her left side of the body.	$n_{Parse} \rightarrow n_{Eval} \rightarrow n_{Out}$	acute_paralysis = true <i>Could not elevate to RD2</i>	Dispatch as RD1
Dispatcher	A vehicle is on its way to you. Please stand by. The emergency call has been processed. Thank you.	n_t		

alike, some scenarios are ambiguous and thus have multiple valid GTs defined. In such cases, each GT defines its final symptom state S_f for one plausible dialogue outcome of the respective scenario. For these cases, a prediction is matched to a GT based on the predicted dialogue outcome. If there is no matching outcome, the sample is not considered for the slot-level comparison. This reflects the ambiguity already present in the original scenario descriptions used for dispatcher training [3].

We evaluate the agent as a simulated emergency call dispatcher along three dimensions relevant to this use case: task performance, dialogue efficiency, and user-perceived quality. Task performance captures the correctness of predicted dialogue outcome and determined symptom state. Dialogue efficiency captures how quick a decision is reached during an interaction. User-perceived quality is the subjective assessment of the quality of the interaction, as perceived by participants and collected through the post-call questionnaire.

5.1 Task performance and dialogue efficiency

For task performance, we distinguish dialogue outcome determination and symptom state elicitation. The former is treated as a single-label multi-class classification task for the predicted dialogue outcome. For each simulated call, the DST produces a final predicted symptom state S_f and determines the predicted dialogue outcome based on it. Task accuracy compares predicted dialogue outcomes with the corresponding GT. Meanwhile, symptom elicitation is treated

Table 3. Metric results comparing the FSM+LLM agent against an LLM-only baseline, grouped by evaluation subset. Mean caller turn count reports standard deviation; median caller turn count reports interquartile range ($Q1, Q3$).

Metric	FSM+LLM	LLM-Only
<i>All dialogues</i>		
Sample count (n)	30	33
Task accuracy	0.50	0.39
Mean caller turn count	4.33 ± 3.09	5.78 ± 2.51
Median caller turn count	4 (3, 4)	5 (4, 8)
<i>Filtered for correct outcomes</i>		
Sample count (n)	15	13
Precision	0.64	0.56
Recall	0.51	0.38
F1	0.54	0.42
Jaccard	0.45	0.29

as a multi-label prediction task over the symptom slots in K_S . Slot-level metrics are computed only for calls with a matching GT based on the predicted dialogue outcome. Unknown slots in both the predicted symptom state S_f and the selected GT state S_{gt} are treated as predicted and true negatives respectively. This decision is grounded in the real world, where such symptoms are also assumed to be absent at the end of an emergency call. We report Precision, recall, F1 score, and Jaccard similarity as per-sample averages over all evaluated dialogues with correct outcome predictions. Metadata slots $m \in M_T$ are excluded from slot-level evaluation.

The results are summarized in Table 3. Over all dialogues, the FSM-based agent achieves higher task accuracy than the LLM-only baseline, corresponding to a relative improvement of 28.2%. The dialogue efficiency is also improved, reducing the mean caller turn count from 5.78 ± 2.51 to 4.33 ± 3.09 which corresponds to a relative reduction of 25.1%. As the slot-level metrics are reliant on the availability of GTs, only those dialogues with correct dialogue outcome classification could be used. For those dialogues, the FSM-based agent consistently outperforms the baseline across slot-level metrics: precision improves by 14.3%, recall by 34.2%, F1 by 28.6%, and Jaccard similarity by 55.2%. Although both policies have close median caller turn counts, Figure 3 shows that dispersion is notably lower for the FSM-based agent.

5.2 User perceived quality

In addition, we report aggregated ratings from a user survey collected per call. The participants were not informed that multiple agents exist. Table 4 lists the survey items. Their aim is to evaluate the effectiveness of communication between the participant and the agent (Q1, Q2), the perceived efficiency of the agent (Q3, Q4), the naturalness of the responses (Q5, Q6) and the overall impression of the conversation (Q7). We received a total of 59 survey responses, meaning that some dialogues are missing survey responses. Dialogue states were recorded separately, which allows these samples to remain in the task-performance analysis. The participants rated the statements using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 (i.e. “Strongly disagree” – “Strongly agree”) of which the results are shown in Figure 4. User perception of the FSM-guided agent and the baseline agent was similar despite the former using a more rigid dialogue policy.

Fig. 3. Distribution of caller turn counts for the FSM+LLM agent and the LLM-only baseline. Box-plots show median, interquartile range, whiskers, and outliers.

Table 4. Survey items used in the post-call questionnaire. Items cover communication effectiveness (Q1–Q2), efficiency (Q3–Q4), naturalness (Q5–Q6), and overall impression (Q7), rated on a 5-point Likert scale from “Strongly disagree” to “Strongly agree”.

Statement	Label
I always knew what I could say at each point in the dialogue.	Q1
The agent understood what I said.	Q2
The agent’s messages were relevant and focused on the situation.	Q3
The agent responded promptly and avoided unnecessary delays during the conversation.	Q4
The agent’s behaviour felt appropriate for this conversation.	Q5
The agent’s messages felt realistic and fluent.	Q6
Overall, this conversation went well.	Q7

5.3 Analysis of Results

Our results show that our FSM-based dialogue policy outperforms the baseline in terms of classification performance, while participants did not perceive meaningful behavioural differences between both agents. Due to the shared components, the improved performance likely reflects the structured dialogue flow, which allows the use of pre-defined questions from Q and more specific prompt design. It also ensures that important questions are asked at the right moment and that the conversation remains focused. The use of Q helps the likelihood of eliciting useful information from users. The content and order of these questions are already optimized by experts to balance likelihood of occurrence

Fig. 4. Mean survey ratings for Q1–Q7 on a 5-point Likert scale for the FSM+LLM agent and the LLM-only baseline; error bars indicate standard deviation.

and severity of symptoms. By omitting the conversation history, we reduce the context of the LLM. Previous research has shown that dependence on the LLM-context is unreliable and leads to performance degradation [5].

When compared to other systems, our results are consistent with the complexity of the task. Much of benchmark-oriented TOD evaluation is built around overly simplistic slot-value dialogue states that do not reflect real-world complexities [32]. At the same time, commonly used datasets under-represent indirect or otherwise unclear user requests which would be difficult to use for slot-filling [17]. Medical emergency calls are more demanding in two aspects. First, as the interaction is time-critical, the order of questions does matter. Delays in critical assessments, such as consciousness and breathing, can significantly delay the recognition of life-threatening situations [26]. Second, there is a pronounced domain gap between participants, unlike in popular TOD domains. Callers often describe the situation in lay and incomplete terms, whereas the system must map these utterances onto sophisticated decision categories. This difficulty has also been observed in other professional domains, where non-expert users struggle to formulate domain-appropriate queries and may omit factors decisive for expert judgment [31]. These properties help explain why stronger dialogue control and precise questioning are particularly beneficial in our setting.

Likewise, we are able to show that our agent finishes these time-critical calls faster. Although both implementations have close median caller turn counts, the interquartile range is substantially smaller for the FSM-based policy than for

the LLM-only baseline. This suggests that our implementation is not only more efficient on average, but also more consistent. The few outliers observed are consistent with its explicit dialogue policy. As the FSM-based agent follows a fixed protocol with explicit clarification and termination decisions, it can occasionally produce very short calls when a terminating dialogue outcome is reached early, but also longer calls when intensive questioning is needed. In the LLM-only baseline, coercing the LLM to follow the protocol to such a level of detail is difficult. This likely leads to a more even distribution, although with far fewer successes. Taken together with the lower slot-level metrics, we conclude that the baseline agent is more prone to longer dialogues without achieving better task performance.

The survey results indicate that participants were unaware of the existence of multiple policies, which we can confirm anecdotally from direct feedback. Without knowledge of the emergency call protocol or the classification output, both systems likely appeared similar from the user’s perspective since both agents produce plausible behaviour (Q3, Q4) and utterances that sounded natural (Q5, Q6). This is nevertheless encouraging as stronger dialogue control is often associated with less natural utterance generation in traditional task-oriented systems and usually struggles to match human variation and fluency [6]. Our results therefore suggest that the FSM-guided hybrid design improves objective performance without degrading perceived interaction quality.

6 Discussion and Conclusions

By decomposing the broad dialogue outcome labels of EMS into detailed symptom slots, the dialogue-based classification process becomes more transparent and enables targeted incremental improvements at the level of individual components. Thus, the modular, FSM-based architecture not only structures the dialogue flow, but also serves as the orchestration layer for specialized LLM prompts. By making hand-off conditions, execution order, and termination criteria explicit, the FSM enables a multi-prompt design in which individual components such as NLU-based slot filling and the termination and follow-up decisions can be invoked in a controlled and traceable manner. The EFSM also supports the inclusion of self-contained subroutines, such as guided CPR or other first-aid instructions. In our experiments, the history-free design made the system cheaper to operate, thus making the solution more attractive for large-scale usage. Although we reduce the reliance on LLMs greatly, the non-determinism inherent to LLMs [25] still causes occasional failure while being difficult to eliminate.

There are several avenues for future improvements to the proposed system. While prompt engineering can enhance NLU and NLG performance, optimizing the definition of the dialogue state B_t for LLM-based slot filling benefit the DST. In particular, the current schema could be improved by refining symptom names for better distinctiveness, by adding richer field descriptions and concrete examples for each symptom to improve overall classification performance and reliability. As the present LLM model selection was motivated primarily by latency considerations, next steps should examine more capable or task-adapted LLMs to better characterize the trade-off between latency and performance, and to assess their potential for improving robustness. Future research may also explore the extension of the system to additional emergency categories, the incorporation of practical guidance instructions, and mechanisms for detecting and managing non-cooperative or adversarial callers. Future user studies should use different randomization to enforce perfectly balanced datasets. While this study explicitly avoided the use of automatic speech recognition (ASR), spoken input may offer a more natural input modality whose impact needs to be evaluated in future work.

Increasing citizen preparedness for emergencies through interactive exercises is a rewarding avenue for raising overall emergency resilience of the population. TOD systems are well-suited for this task, as they can provide realistic simulations to a wide audience, while being cost-effective and scalable. This work presents an autonomous dialogue agent for improving emergency call preparedness. Transparency of stepwise classification is achieved by decomposing

high-level categories into semantically meaningful slots. Dialogue flow is controlled by an EFSM that maintains a high degree of structure while avoiding state explosion. Relative to a purely LLM-based baseline, the approach improves both efficiency and accuracy while limiting LLM-made decisions and reducing erroneous NLG.

7 Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 101121134 (B-Prepared). Further the Integrated Leitstelle (ILS) munich assisted significantly in the design of the dialogue agent.

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